

Supplementary Materials

Tool selection:

Strategy papers are usually published as PDF files. Therefore, lossless representation of these artifacts is essential for qualitative analysis. The web application QDAcity was used for the initial coding, as it enables collaboration and allows PDF files to be imported and coded without converting them, for example into plain text. QDAcity is still in the beta phase, which is why some functions have not yet been implemented. The tool worked sufficient for the initial coding and revision. However, the subsequent evaluation of the codes, in particular the review of critical cases and the interpretation of the codes in the further progress, were carried out within structured spreadsheet files.

Coding guidelines:

The coding was carried out in according to the coding rules that had been deductively defined beforehand. For purposes of later interpretation, introductory sentences were usually included in the segment. However, no more than one paragraph was ever accepted as a single segment. Bullet points or headings were usually coded as well to create contexts for later classification and interpretation.

Table 1: Code Matrix with Frequency, exported from QDAcity.

Code	DE 2018	DE 2020	NL 2019	NL 2024	UK 2025 (Report)	UK 2025 (Response)
A1: Objectives	15	19	14	33	7	6
A2: Use Cases	10	27	16	31	4	4
A3: Capacity Building	27	32	39	20	17	18
A4: Implementation Logic	2	7	7	5	15	17
B1: Regulatory References	23	22	16	27	1	5
B2: Oversight Structures	2	4	6	18	2	0
B3: Normative Principles	34	36	54	38	17	16
B4: Assurance Mechanisms	8	8	4	10	4	1
C1: Infrastructure	24	24	5	6	28	30
C2: Partnerships	18	7	27	12	11	25
C3: Ecosystem Facilitation	31	82	22	8	12	10
C4: Multi-Level Coordination	24	16	16	16	2	1

Table 2: Coding Rules “Adaptor”

ID	SUBDIMENSION	DEFINITION	INCLUSION / EXCLUSION	VERBATIM EXAMPLES
A1	Objectives	Strategic goals for AI in administration (e.g., efficiency, personalization).	Incl.: Public sector	Identifying successful pilots that can be applied in different settings to support citizens (e.g. to <u>reduce waiting lists</u> or <u>minimise time and cost to complete paperwork</u>) and rolling them out beyond organisational boundaries. (UK 2025)
			Excl.: Private sector only	These include digital trial fields in agriculture, which show how digital and AI technologies can be optimally deployed to <u>protect the environment</u> , <u>improve animal welfare</u> and <u>biodiversity</u> , and <u>facilitate work</u> . (DE 2020)
A2	Use Cases	Concrete applications (e.g., chatbots, predictive analytics).	Incl.: Public sector	Government agencies such as the police, the Netherlands Enterprise Agency and P-Direkt (the Shared Service Centre for HRM of the Dutch government) <u>develop a chatbot</u> . (NL 2019)
			Excl.: Private sector only	For the music industry <u>generative AI</u> can act as a catalyst for creativity and innovation. In this area, it is able to <u>generate new compositions</u> , <u>creating new melodies, harmonies and rhythms</u> that can inspire or support musicians in their work. (NL 2024)
A3	Capacity Building	Skills, training, organizational change.	Incl. Public sector	Specific support to hire external AI talent. Creation of a technical senior civil servant stream, benchmarking of internal AI -related role pay to at least 75% of private-sector rate and a technical AI recruitment screening process.
			Excl. Private sector only	We will use our Mittelstand 4.0 centres of excellence and our centre of excellence for digital skilled crafts to strengthen SMEs’ competitiveness and ability to innovate in a lasting way; (DE 2018)
A4	Implementation Logic	Pathways like scan-pilot-scale.		Scale and open source 1-2 public sector-led AI solutions that are currently in pilot phase. (UK 2025)

Table 3: Coding Rules “Regulator”

ID	SUBDIMENSION	DEFINITION	INCLUSION / EXCLUSION	VERBATIM EXAMPLES
B1	Regulatory References	Laws/standards (e.g., EU AI Act).	Incl.: Binding rules	This will help increase the availability and quality of the data that is used by the public sector, and, indirectly, for research, business and other purposes. We will assess whether the advisory office set out in Section 12a of the eGovernment Act needs to be further expanded. (DE 2018)
			Excl.: Voluntary guidelines	The starting point here is a values-driven approach, in line with the Value-Driven Digitalisation Work Agenda, the ‘Agenda Coalities voor de Digitale Samenleving’, the Digital Economy Strategy and the EU’s coordinated plan on AI. (NL 2024)
B2	Oversight Structures	Institutions (e.g., AI safety institutes).		A ‘Rijks AI-validatieteam’ (Government AI Validation Team) facilitates publicly available benchmarking and tooling (such as bias detection, based on democratic input, for instance) to provide guardrails for responsible generative AI in the Netherlands. (NL 2024)
B3	Normative Principles	Public values (e.g., transparency, non-discrimination).		Common principles such as the internationally verified and accepted FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles offer a good basis for the standards, tools and training per domain or sector. (NL 2019)
B4	Assurance Mechanisms	Tools like audits, sandboxes.	Incl: Procedural safeguards.	A Government AI Validation Team facilitates publicly available benchmarking and tooling (such as bias detection, based on democratic input, for instance) to provide guardrails for responsible generative AI in the Netherlands. (NL 2024)
			Excl: Awareness campaigns	NA

Table 4: Coding Rules “Orchestrator”

ID	SUBDIMENSION	DEFINITION	INCLUSION / EXCLUSION	VERBATIM EXAMPLES
C1	Infrastructure	Data/compute provision (e.g., sovereign clouds).	Incl.	Build public sector data collection infrastructure and finance the creation of new high - value data sets that meet public sector, academia and startup needs. (UK 2025)
			Excl. Unspecific	Set out, within six months, a long-term plan for UK’s AI infrastructure needs, backed by a 10-year investment commitment.
C2	Partnerships	Public-private coalitions.	Incl: Formal collaborations.	We work together in public-private partnerships, including in the Dutch AI Coalition, to seize the societal and economic opportunities of AI. (NL 2019)
			Excl: Consultations.	An expert forum that considered research-related aspects of the Key Points Paper underpinning the Artificial Intelligence Strategy was held in Berlin on 13 September 2018. The online consultation considered these aspects also. (DE 2020)
C3	Ecosystem Facilitation	Funding or hubs for innovation.	Incl: Administratively enabled.	Further developing the Centre of Excellence for Innovative Procurement (KOINNO) to increase the proportion of innovations procured in the total volume of public procurement in Germany (DE 2020)
			Excl: Research-only	We will further develop our existing Centres of Excellence for AI at supra-regional level, establish additional ones, and develop them into a national network of at least twelve centres and application hubs. (DE 2018)
C4	Multi-Level Coordination	Integration in international bilateral or multilateral agreements / organizations	Incl: clearly defined organizations, international partners, or agreements	The Netherlands participates in the EuroHPC partnership under Horizon Europe in the field of high- performance computing (HPC), enabling Dutch companies and knowledge institutions to participate in European projects on HPC and quantum computing. (NL 2024)
			Excl: unspecific calls for cooperation	DSIT will set out its approach to international collaborations as part of its long-term compute strategy. (UK 2025)

Discourse and Intercoder Agreements:

After completing the first three of the six documents, the primary coder identified coding categories that required further analysis. The identified codes for categories B1, B2, B3, and B4 were carefully reviewed by the coding partner. The total number of segments and the codes to be discussed are listed in the following tables.

	B1	B2	B3	B4
<i>N_{Total}</i>	9	2	66	7
<i>N_{Discursive}</i>	3	0	5	1

Following codes where coded as B1 by the initial coder:

Document	Segment	Note by coding partner	Intercoder-Agreement
NL 2019	The Strategic Action Plan for AI is an agenda that is updated annually. The House of Representatives will be informed about the implementation of the policy actions set out in this Action Plan (see Appendix 1 for an overview) as part of the progress report and update of the Dutch Digitalisation Strategy. In addition, the various ministries apply their own evaluation and monitoring systems for the actions for which they are responsible. The progress of the AI approach is on the agenda of the National Council for the Dutch Digitalisation Strategy. (NL 2019)	I'm not sure to what extent this code fits into regulatory references.	Exclude, since the focus is on situating the AI strategy and its procedural development within governmental processes, rather than analyzing specific regulatory measures derived from the strategy.
NL 2019	Research into design principles for AI in the legal domain (CWI, the national research institute for mathematics and computer science, TNO the Netherlands organisation for applied scientific research, the UvA, University of Amsterdam and the OM, the Dutch public prosecution service)	This is about research on legal topics. Not B1.	Exclude.
UK 2025	Our transformative planning reforms will make it easier to build the data centres that are the engines of the AI age.	No relevance to B1.	Exclude, as this refers to the Planning and Infrastructure Bill, which, as a draft, does not yet have regulatory authority.

Following codes were coded as B3 by the initial coder:

Document	Segment	Note by coding partner	Intercoder-Agreement
UK 2025	Graduates from some leading AI institutions, such as the Indian Institutes of Technology and (since 2020) Carnegie Mellon University in the US, are not currently included in the High Potential Individual visa eligibility list. Government should take steps to develop new pathways, and strengthen existing ones, to support these graduates. It should also explore how best to address wider barriers like the cost and complexity of visas which create obstacles for startups and deter overseas talent from relocating to the UK.		Set code B1, as this concerns immigration regulations.
UK 2025	Require all regulators to publish annually how they have enabled innovation and growth driven by AI in their sector. To ensure accountability, this should include transparent metrics such as timelines to publish guidance, make licence decisions and report on resources allocated to AI-focused work. Even with these initiatives, individual regulators may still lack the incentives to promote innovation at the scale of the government's ambition. If evidence demonstrates that is the case, government should consider more radical changes to our regulatory model for AI, for example by empowering a central body with a mandate and higher risk tolerance to promote innovation across the economy. Such a body could have expertise and statutory powers to issue pilot sandbox licences for AI products that override sector regulations, taking on liability for all related risks. This approach could initially be explored and piloted for specific AI applications at small scale.	Code as B4 in addition to B3	Code as B4
NL 2019	There is no generally valid definition of AI that is consistently used by all stakeholders. We use the European Commission's description of AI: 'AI refers to systems that display intelligent behaviour by analysing their environment and taking actions – with some degree of autonomy – to achieve specific goals'. For an understandable explanation of what AI is, everyone is invited to take the National AI course. This course briefly explains what this technology is all about. Participation is free.	Is that prescriptive? I'd take that out.	Just for definitional purposes; exclude.
NL 2019	For more information on the definition of AI, see the Independent High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 'A Definition of AI: Main Capabilities and Scientific Disciplines', April 2019.	Same here. I don't see this as a prescriptive statement. I'd remove it.	Exclude.
NL 2019	Research into design principles for AI in the legal domain (CWI, the national research institute for mathematics and computer science, TNO the Netherlands organisation for applied scientific research, the UvA, University of Amsterdam and the OM, the Dutch public prosecution service).	Same here. I don't see this as a prescriptive statement. I'd remove it.	Exclude.

Following codes where coded as B4 by the initial coder:

Document	Segment	Note by coding partner	Intercoder-Agreement
DE 2018	The Federal Government will examine ways of auditing AI for use in companies.	B4 or B1? (Or even B2, even if not institution-specific)?	Leave the coding as is (B4), since auditing and benchmarking should be viewed more as an assurance mechanism than as regulatory references (B1). No B2, since no institution is named.

Parallel codes identified by initial coder:

To ensure consistency in the coding process, the authors reviewed segments with potential code overlaps at an early stage of the analysis. The purpose of this exercise was not to establish statistical intercoder reliability, but rather to enhance transparency regarding ambiguous coding situations and to clarify the conceptual boundaries between categories. Cases included in the table were therefore selected because they raised interpretative questions about the appropriate assignment of codes or about the distinction between closely related analytical categories.

In situations where initial coding diverged, the authors discussed the interpretative basis of the respective codes and the underlying analytical intent of the text segment. When a clear conceptual rationale supported multiple interpretations, segments were coded with multiple codes. In other cases, one code was prioritized based on the dominant policy function reflected in the passage. If disagreements could not be fully resolved without imposing an artificial boundary between categories, the overlap was retained and documented as an analytical tension.

Document	Segment	Intercoder-Agreement
DE 2020	One of the most promising applications is in urban air mobility, the pilotless flying of the future. This makes it crucial for AI systems for aviation-relevant applications to be specially protected against cyber attacks. Researchers are already working on this at full steam, too.	A2 only, exclude A1
DE 2020	Holding AI challenges and establishing a German award for “AI made in Germany”.	A3 and C3 with Tension : How does the administration view itself? As part of the broader labor market vs. solely from an internal perspective.
DE 2020	Further developing the Centre of Excellence for Innovative Procurement (KOINNO) to increase the proportion of innovations procured in the total volume of public procurement in Germany	A3 and C3 after Discussion since KOINNO is acquiring procurement capabilities within the German public sector.
DE 2020	The Federal Government itself can support start-ups and SMEs with AI solutions	B1 and B3

	by giving greater consideration to these in public contracts in compliance with the requirements under budgetary and public procurement law.	
DE	The Federal Government welcomes the approach proposed by the European Commission in the White Paper on Artificial Intelligence of reviewing the EU's existing legal framework to determine whether existing legislation duly reflects the risks and requirements of AI applications and can be effectively enforced or whether and what amendments or new legislation may be necessary. Here, the question to be answered is whether the current legal framework on product safety and product liability is sufficient for AI systems embedded in products or whether new provisions need to be created, also when it comes to the issue of legal certainty. In particular, the Federal Government believes it makes sense in the interest of principle-based regulation to draft central principles for trustworthy AI which are harmonised across the EU. In addition to this, the Federal Government is actively supporting the processes and initiatives that have already been launched at the level of the EU and the Council of Europe in this regard.	B1 and B3
NL	UNESCO is also active in the field of AI and is also a partner in the Global Partnership on AI (GPAI). In 2021, a recommendation on AI ethics was adopted, partly at the initiative of the Netherlands. This was followed by policy papers on ChatGPT and AI Foundational Models in relation to the recommendation in 2023. The Netherlands aims to maintain focus on implementing this recommendation, emphasising the connection between AI, ethics, and human rights.	B1 and B3
DE 2020	This poses new challenges to the regulatory framework, which in the single market for products is currently shaped by the New Legislative Framework (NLF) - and here in particular to the quality infrastructure consisting of metrology, norms and standardisation, accreditation, conformity assessment and market surveillance. The task is to further develop the existing structures into systems for safe and trustworthy AI.	B1 and B4, exclude C1
NL 2024	The establishment of an AI Advisory Council, (or Rapid Response Team AI), is being considered at the highest level to provide the government with short- and long-term advice.	B2 only, exclude B4 and C3
NL 2024	A 'Rijks AI-validatieteam' (Government AI Validation Team) facilitates publicly available benchmarking and tooling (such as bias detection, based on democratic input, for instance) to provide guardrails for responsible generative AI in the Netherlands.	B2 and B4
DE 2020	In addition to issues relating to environmental impacts, data and consumer protection issues also have to be duly taken into account.	B3 only, exclude B1
DE 2020	At the same time, the new platform is designed to reduce the administrative and auditing workload at the enforcement authorities and registries involved in the scheme.	B3 and B4, exclude A1 after Discussion: This example involves a risk impact assessment (AI leads to increased energy

		consumption). The platform's "objective" is to evaluate this efficiently and effectively for enforcement agencies. The platform itself is not AI, but only evaluates AI. Does this align with A1 or A in general? Can A1 also assign negative implications as an objective? B3 applies here as well, since resource conservation constitute a normative principle. The last sentence does, after all, represent an assurance mechanism.
DE 2020	Additionally, the Federal Government is developing a Civic Data Lab to prepare data sets shared and provided by various civil society actors and access and exchange structures, and Civic Tech Labs for Green for the participatory development and provision of green tech tools.	C1 and C3
UK 2025	Set out, within six months, a long-term plan for UK's AI infrastructure needs, backed by a 10-year investment commitment.	neither B1 nor C1